

Effects of Ground Temperature, Ground Material Properties and Body Position on Postmortem Axial Heat Transfer

Sipho Mfolozi¹

Abstract—The effects of body position, ground temperature and ground material properties on postmortem axial heat transfer were investigated to inform numerical death-time estimation procedures. A postmortem cooling simulation in unforced convection conditions with no ground contact served as the control. Postmortem cooling was simulated in the supine position on a modelled cold concrete floor and on a domestic-type heated floor. Permanent axial displacement of the antemortem central isotherm (ACI) and postmortem central isotherms (PCI) away from the cold concrete ground and towards the heated floor was observed due to the supine body position. Both ground types absorbed heat from the body and were not infinite heat sinks. The postmortem temperature plateau (PMTP) was significantly shortened by both ground types, being shortest on the heated floor. Legacy methods of death-time estimation based on single-point (rectal) thermometry cannot detect ACI/PCI displacement that determines the measured core temperature value. They are based on the supine position and do not apply corrective factors for ground-associated variables or non-supine positions. All these constitute sources of uncertainty. Realistic modelling of body position and ground-associated thermophysical variables is essential to correctly account for their effects during postmortem cooling, and use of the novel multipoint axial thermometry (MAT) protocol of death-time estimation, which can detect ACI/PCI displacement and simulate body position and pose, is advocated for this.

Keywords — ACI/PCI displacement, ground material properties, MAT, concrete, heated floor

1. INTRODUCTION

POSTMORTEM axial heat transfer is characterised by perpetual formation of progressively cooler isotherms on the skin, which gradually reduce in radius as they propagate towards the antemortem central isotherm (ACI). Consequently, the ACI diameter also gradually reduces and its temperature manifests as the postmortem temperature plateau (PMTP) when recorded by single-point thermometry [1]. Postmortem cooling under natural/unforced convection conditions, in which external cooling by thermal conduction does not occur, results in a uniform rate of cooling along the body circumference. However, in the real world, deaths scenarios for which death-time estimation is often called upon are usually characterised by part of the decedent's body being in contact with a ground surface of sorts, through which heat transfer occurs by thermal conduction, while heat transfer in other parts of the body in contact with air occurs by

thermal convection. Effects of asymmetrical postmortem cooling of skin by thermal conduction, particularly as a result of ground thermophysical properties, on this postmortem axial heat transfer process are presently unknown.

Literature on empiric postmortem cooling observations used to formulate today's gold standard death-time estimation methods, such as the rectal temperature nomogram method [2], is antiquated and there are no studies that specifically investigated effects of ground temperature, ground material properties and body position on postmortem heat transfer. Material properties of a ground surface that affect the postmortem heat transfer process are its density (ρ), thermal conductivity (k), heat capacity (C), and temperature. In such literature, ground material properties were not stated or standardised. Typical ground surfaces of postmortem cooling included wood [3 – 7], cement [3], metal [8 – 11], rubber [4] and bed [12,13]. Some studies did not describe the type of ground on which

¹Department of Forensic Medicine, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban 4000, South Africa
Email: siphomfolozi@gmail.com

bodies were placed. In other studies, bodies were placed on more than one type of ground surface before the study commenced (e.g. at the original place of death, inside the hearse/ambulance during transportation to the mortuary, and inside the mortuary during final observation). Some authors [5] theorised about the effects of thermal conductivity of a ground-surface on the rate of postmortem cooling but did not conduct studies to demonstrate them.

Later empiric studies of postmortem cooling adopted the so-called 'standard cooling conditions', defined as *a naked body in the supine position on a thermally neutral surface in constant-temperature air with no wind and no strong thermal radiation* [9, 14 – 16]. However, ground-associated thermal properties were still not stated, and it was not clear whether the stated 'thermal neutrality' of the ground was towards the body or the air. Ground thermal neutrality towards either would have meant that their respective material and thermal properties were identical to those of the ground, but this was never demonstrated to be the case. In these studies, the thermometer would be placed in the rectum at the beginning of observation. Thereafter, the body would be left to cool undisturbed in the supine position while rectal temperature was continuously recorded until it reached ambient air temperature. No study investigated postmortem cooling in non-supine positions, despite dead bodies sometimes being found in such positions in the real world. In real-world scenarios requiring death-time estimation, a body may have cooled for a number of hours while in a non-supine position. Such a body would need to first be placed in the prone position by the pathologist to enable rectal thermometry. Effects of such body positions and changes on postmortem axial heat transfer are presently unknown. None of the legacy methods used today applies corrective factors for ground-associated variables and non-supine body positions. This represents a potential source of uncertainty, which this study investigates.

Numerical methods of simulating postmortem cooling and estimating the death interval first described around the beginning of the 21st century possess the ability to realistically model the ground surface, although they do not necessarily always do so. For example, in applying the finite element model [6] to estimate the death interval in five real-world cases, the ground was treated as an infinite heat reservoir that rapidly conducted the warmth coming from the body. That approach was deemed convenient because the ground did not need to be modelled by finite elements itself, as long as the 3D computational human model was kept touching the ground fixed at a constant environmental or ground temperature. No numerical study of postmortem cooling has examined effects of ground temperature, material properties and body posture on postmortem axial heat transfer recently-described as being characterised by a shrinking ACI with simultaneous formation of cooler circular isotherms on the skin that propagate inwards [1]. The objective of this study was thus

to apply numerical analysis methods to understand these effects to, in turn, better inform numerical death-time estimation procedures.

2. METHOD

A high anatomical-fidelity 3D computational human model built from magnetic resonance images of a 32-year-old, 70.2 kg, 1.77-meter tall, healthy, living male, which consisted of 247 anatomically segmented organs, was used as a human surrogate [7]. Its antemortem axial temperature distribution was first numerically approximated using materials and methods applied by Mfolozi [8]. The air temperature was 22°C. A numerical study of postmortem cooling in 14°C air under unforced/natural convection conditions, in which there was no ground contact [1], was first performed as the control study against which simulations for the present study would be compared.

2.1. Postmortem cooling supine on cold concrete

To investigate effects of ground material properties, low ground temperature and the supine body position on postmortem axial heat transfer, a concrete ground object measuring 2000 mm x 600 mm x 300 mm was modelled in the simulation software (Fig. 1). Its upper surface was slightly concave longitudinally to ensure continuous contact with the 3D computational human model. The density value applied was 2400 kgm⁻³ for M50-grade concrete [9], the thermal conductivity value was 0.8 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹ [10], and the specific heat capacity value was 960 Jkg⁻¹K. The 3D computational human model was placed supine on the concrete ground model object, and contact points were the occiput, shoulder blades, buttocks, posterior surfaces of the thighs, hamstrings, and posterior surfaces of the heels. The initial condition of the concrete model object was 14°C. The initial condition of the 3D computational human model was the solution of the approximated antemortem axial temperature distribution, as discussed earlier. The air temperature was 14°C, the boundary type was 'mixed' and the heat transfer coefficient (h) applied was 3.4 Wm⁻²K [11]. The simulation interval was 18000 s (5 hours) using a 1 s time-step factor. The resultant grid generated by the gridding software consisted of 5.9374E10⁷ cells. Voxels were created using the simulation software's voxel tool.

Fig. 1. The modelled concrete ground object measuring 2000mm x 600mm x 300mm, with the 3D computational human model placed on it. Image A indicates side view, image B indicates oblique view.

Fig. 2. The modelled heated floor object (brown) measuring 1930mm x 600mm x 20mm, placed between the 3D computational human model and the modelled concrete ground object (beige). Image A indicates side view, image B indicates oblique view.

2.2 Postmortem cooling supine on domestic-type heated floor

To investigate the effects of a heated floor and the supine body position on postmortem axial heat transfer, a longitudinally concave, heated floor object measuring 1930 mm x 600 mm x 20 mm was modelled in the simulation software and placed on the corresponding longitudinally concave surface of the modelled concrete ground object (Fig. 2). The heated floor was assigned a Neumann boundary condition to enable it to be a heat source. Being a boundary condition, the heated floor could not be assigned material properties but was assigned a $+40 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ heat-flux value, wherein the plus sign denoted it as a heat source (and a minus sign would denote it as a heat sink). This heat flux value produced a 25°C temperature field of the heated floor, which constituted its initial condition. The 3D computational human model was placed supine on the modelled heated floor at the beginning of the post-mortem cooling simulation, and the resultant skin contact-points were identical to those observed on the modelled concrete ground. Beneath the heated floor was the modelled concrete ground object discussed earlier. The initial condition of the 3D computational human model was the solution of the approximated antemortem axial temperature distribution discussed earlier. The initial condition, air temperature, boundary type, heat transfer coefficient, simulation interval, voxel sequence and time-step factor were identical to those applied for cooling on

concrete. The grid consisted of $6.2278\text{E}10^7$ cells.

3. RESULT

3.1. Postmortem cooling supine on cold concrete

Simulated post-mortem axial heat transfer on the modelled cold concrete surface indicated many similarities to the control simulation [1], in which successively cooler isotherms formed on the skin and propagated towards the body centre and in which the radius of the 37.4°C ACI simultaneously and gradually reduced over time. However, the following significant differences were noted:

- The skin areas on which the 3D computational human model was in contact with the concrete ground surface showed consistently lower temperatures compared to the rest of the body at any given PMI, throughout the simulated cooling period. This was attributed to accelerated heat transfer by thermal conduction in these areas.
- The ACI was permanently displaced away from the cold concrete ground surface as a result of consistently lower temperatures on contact points with skin, as mentioned above. This ACI displacement was towards the anterior surface of the body, on account of the 3D computational human model's supine position.

- c) The ACI in the 3D computational human model (the PMTP) lasted 9000 s (2 hrs 30 mins), compared to 3 hrs 51 mins in the control simulation.
- d) The concrete model object showed a progressive increase in its own temperature, which originated from contact points with the 3D computational human model. In axial view, these isotherms became semi-circular as they gradually expanded deeper into the concrete model object. As a result, the temperature of the concrete ground surface gradually increased.

Fig. 3 indicates the effects of cold concrete ground on post-mortem axial heat transfer.

Fig. 3. Simulated post-mortem cooling on cold concrete. Nine axial thermograms taken at successively longer PMIs indicating permanent ACI/PCI displacement, persistently lower skin contact-points and isotherms inside the modelled concrete (black). The temperature scale range is 14°C to 41.7°C.

3.2 Postmortem cooling supine on domestic-type heated floor

Simulated post-mortem axial heat transfer on a domestic-type heated floor model object also indicated many similarities to the control simulation under unforced/natural convection conditions [1]. However, the following significant differences were noted:

- a) At death, the ACI was already displaced to the posterior aspect of the 3D computational human model, being significantly shorter in the frontal axis than in the control simulation. The anterior aspect of the body was occupied by a much cooler C-shaped isotherm.
- b) The ACI/PCIs remained displaced posteriorly for the remainder of postmortem cooling, while the cooler C-shaped isotherm also remained on the anterior aspect of the body. The result was that the skin temperature on the anterior surface of the body remained fairly constant throughout the 5-hour simulated postmortem cooling interval.
- c) Cooler isotherms formed on all sides around the permanently displaced ACI. The ACI radius in the frontal axis was therefore significantly less, giving the ACI/PCIs an ellipsoid shape.
- d) The ACI in the 3D computational human model existed for 5400 s (1 hr 30 mins) due to its ellipsoid shape.
- e) The temperature of the heated floor at the contact points of the 3D computational human model increased above the heated floor's initial temperature of 25°C, creating a hot silhouette of the shape of the human model (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4 indicates effects of a heated floor on postmortem axial heat transfer.

4. DISCUSSION

The persistently lower skin temperatures observed on the 3D computational human model's concrete contact points, as well as the shortened PMTP (the ACI's lifespan), were both attributed to accelerated heat transfer by thermal conduction. The total surface area of these contact points was a small fraction of the body's total skin surface area, the remainder of which cooled in free air under unforced convection conditions. Displacement of the ACI and

Fig. 4. Simulated post-mortem cooling on heated floor. Nine axial thermograms taken at successively longer PMIs indicating permanent ACI/PCI displacement and persistently lower temperatures on the anterior aspect of the body. The temperature scale range is 14.2°C to 39.2°C.

succeeding postmortem central isotherms (PCI) away from the cold concrete ground was attributed to the low initial temperature of concrete compared to the ACI temperature. The posterior direction of ACI and PCI displacement was the result of the supine body position. Therefore, it can be stated that the final ACI/PCI displacement position in postmortem cooling where ground temperature is lower than body temperature, is determined by body position.

The modelled cold concrete ground surface absorbed heat away from the body, as expected, but such heat transfer

Fig. 5. A thermogram of the heated floor after 5hrs postmortem cooling indicating a 'hot silhouette' on where the 3D computational human model was placed (not shown). The temperature scale is 21°C to 36.2°C.

invariably increased the temperature of the concrete floor, which, in turn, affected the rate of subsequent heat transfer from the body. The cold concrete could, therefore, not be considered an infinite heat reservoir, as was the case in the finite element model [6]. The understanding of an infinite heat reservoir ground is its ability to absorb infinite quantities of heat without itself, the body or the rate of heat transfer being affected by the absorbed heat. The axial isotherm in the concrete furthest from the contact points had not reached the bottom limit of the concrete at the 5-hour limit of the simulation. This was regarded to imply that the modelled 600mm thickness of the concrete was sufficient for this for numerical death-time estimation procedures to limit the model size and conserve computational resources.

The effect of the heated floor on postmortem axial heat transfer was unexpected and, initially, appeared paradoxical. First, the heated floor was expected to slow the rate of postmortem cooling, or even cause postmortem heat transfer back to the 3D computational human model. However, postmortem heat transfer was demonstrated to occur *from* the 3D computational human model to the heated floor, despite the latter having a positive heat flux value. The hot silhouette on the heated floor (Fig. 5), whose temperature after heat transfer was higher than the initial 25°C, was proof of this. Secondly, the PMTP length on the heated floor was expected to be longer than the PMTP length documented in free-air cooling [1]. Instead, it was demonstrably shorter. These observations were attributed to heat transfer by thermal conduction into the heated floor, which followed a temperature gradient from the 37.4°C ACI to the 25°C heated floor that existed at the beginning of postmortem cooling. It was postulated that heat transfer to the heated floor would have continued until a 25°C PCI existed in the 3D computational human model, after which heat transfer would stop. However, the 5-hour limit of the simulation was not sufficient to prove/disprove this hypothesis. Finally, the PMTP length on the heated floor was 60 mins shorter than the PMTP length on the cold concrete. The extent of ACI displacement from the central position of control unforced convection cooling

study appeared to influence the extent by which PMTP length was reduced. ACI displacement on the heated floor was greater than that observed on the cold concrete floor (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. A comparison of ACI/PCI positions during postmortem cooling in the supine position. The dotted line passes through the centre of the 'control study' ACI (image A). Image B indicates anterior ACI/PCI displacement observed in cold concrete cooling. Image C indicates posterior ACI/PCI displacement observed in heated floor cooling.

The constantly low skin temperature noted on the anterior surface of the body throughout the 5-hour simulated PMI on the heated floor has significant implications for skin temperature-based methods of death time estimation [23, 24].

5. CONCLUSION

The temperature and material properties of a ground surface on which postmortem cooling occurs evidently cause permanent ACI/PCI axial displacement compared to post-mortem cooling in free air under unforced/natural convection conditions. The final extent of ACI/PCI axial displacement depends on the total surface area of the skin in contact with the ground. The final position of ACI/PCI displacement in the body depends on the body position (supine, prone, lateral). This is self-evident without the need to conduct separate simulations to demonstrate the effects of different body positions. ACI/PCI displacement, on the other hand, determines the extent of PMTP shortening, the core temperature value measured by subsequent single-point thermometry, and, ultimately, the death-time estimation calculation made using such a single-point thermometry value. It can be concluded the action of first placing a body found dead in the prone position to facilitate rectal thermometry causes ACI/PCI displacement from their original position to a new axial position, depending on ground temperature. This likely changes the measured rectal temperature value had body position been supine or left unchanged. Placing a body prone for rectal thermometry therefore itself introduces uncertainty. The author attributes the responsiveness of single-point core body temperature to body position, reported by Abraham et al. [12], to ACI/PCI displacement resulting from change of body position, as demonstrated in this paper.

Single-point thermometry does not have the capacity to detect any ACI/PCI displacement in the body when

present. By affecting PMTP length, it is now clear that the ground-associated variables investigated in this paper are additional PMTP constants in the cooling formula that must be quantified for each body found dead, as originally suggested by Marshall [13]. Their random variation from one death scene to another constitutes a source of uncertainty for legacy methods. While the retrofitting of their corrective factors to legacy methods is technically feasible, these methods have a number of inherent sources of uncertainty that would need to simultaneously be addressed. These include single-point thermometry itself, realistic approximation of the antemortem axial temperature distribution based on estimated antemortem physical activity, non-standardisation of thermometry-depth and body radius, non-standardisation of the postmortem interval at the time of thermometry as it affects the PMTP length at that time, and application of an estimated average air temperature value done because the time of death is unknown.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

To overcome uncertainties of legacy methods, this paper proposes use of the novel multipoint axial thermometry (MAT) protocol of death-time estimation [14], which numerically models the ground surface, its temperature and material properties, as well as body position and posture. Material properties of the ground are sourced from the literature, and ground temperature at the time of MAT may be assumed to be equilibrated with ambient air or measured using infrared thermography in the case of domestic underfloor heating (Fig. 7), or ice-covered ground. Surface texture of the ground, and body position and posture may be modelled using laser scanned 3D images of the death scene [15]. The protocol applies a novel MAT device [16] consisting of 64 tandem electronic body-temperature sensors that can collectively detect ACI/PCI displacement inside the body. The MAT device can be inserted into any body part without the need to first reposition the body into the prone position for rectal thermometry. The 3-axis spatial orientation in which the MAT device is inserted into the body determines the direction of the detected ACI/PCI displacement, as it would be asymmetrical to body centre. This 3-axis orientation is duplicated during insertion of the virtual MAT device into a morphometrically comparable 3D human computational model during the numerical simulation phase of the protocol. This duplication ensures comparability of the measured and simulated MAT profiles during the comparison phase of the protocol. In addition, the 3D computational human models applied in the MAT protocol are posable, i.e., the angles of their major joints, such as the knee, hip, shoulder and elbow,

can be manipulated through ranges in the three axes (x, y, z) to pose the 3D human models in the likeness of the dead body as documented at a death scene. This posing results in close numerical approximation of the total skin surface area in contact with the ground.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The research was funded by the National Research Foundation (NRF) of South Africa under the Thuthuka PhD Track funding instrument, fund number TK14042966700. Sim4Life®, the biological simulation software that includes a thermal solver, was generously provided by Zurich MedTech, Switzerland. The 3D computational phantoms were generously provided by IT'IS Foundation, Switzerland. I acknowledge contributions by Professors AG Malan, T Bello-Ochende and LJ Martin of the University of Cape Town, South Africa.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Mfolozi, "Postmortem axial heat transfer," *Journal of Numerical Thanatochronometry*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 10-18, 2021.
- [2] C. Henßge, "Death time estimation in case work. I. The rectal temperature time of death nomogram," *Forensic Science International*, vol. 38, no. 3-4, pp. 209-236, 1988.
- [3] G. De Saram, G. Webster and N. Kathirgamatamby, "Postmortem temperature and the time of death," *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 562-577, 1955.
- [4] H. Lyle and F. Cleveland, "Determination of the time of death by heat loss," *Journal of Forensic Science*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 11-24, 1956.
- [5] A. Taylor and D. Wilks, "On the cooling of the human body after death: inferences respecting the time of death, observations of temperature made in 100 cases," *Guy's Hospital Report*, pp. 1-33, 1863.
- [6] G. Mall and W. Eisenmenger, "Estimation of time since death by heat-flow Finite-element model part II: application to non-standard cooling conditions and preliminary results in practical casework.," *Legal Medicine*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 69-80, 2005.
- [7] M. Gosselin, E. Neufeld, H. Moser, E. Huber, S. Farcito, L. Gerber, M. Jedensjö, I. Hilber, F. Di Gennaro, B. Lloyd, E. Cherubini, D. Szvzerba, W. Kainz and N. Kuster, "Development of a new generation of high-resolution anatomical models for medical device evaluation: the Virtual Population

Fig. 7. Image A is a photograph of a death scene in a guest house attended by the author. The victim was an adult female who was manually throttled and found supine on a tiled bathroom floor with underfloor heating switched on. Image B is an infrared thermogram of the bathroom floor with underfloor heating switched on. It was taken using a FLIR camera after the body was removed and room cleaned. Image C is an infrared thermogram of the bathroom floor with heating switched off.

- 3.0," *Physics in Medicine and Biology*, vol. 59, no. 18, pp. 5287-5303, 2014.
- [8] S. Mfolozi, "Approximation of antemortem axial temperature distribution for death-time estimation," *Journal of Numerical Thanatochronometry*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1-8, 2021.
- [9] S. Kitouni and H. Houari, "Lightweight concrete with Algerian limestone dust. Part I: Study on 30% replacement to normal aggregate at early age.," *Cerâmica*, vol. 59, no. 352, pp. 600-608, 2013.
- [10] H. Young, University Physics, Reading, Massachusetts: Addison Wesley Publication Company, 1992.
- [11] R. de Dear, "Convective and radiative heat transfer coefficients for individual human body segments," *International Journal of Biometeorology*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 141-156, 1997.
- [12] J. Abraham, L. Cheng, L. Vallez and T. Wei, "Using cadaver temperatures to estimate time of death: A case-specific numerical approach: A case specific approach," *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, vol. 00, pp. 1-11, 2022.
- [13] T. Marshal and F. Hoare, "Estimating the time of death. The rectal cooling after death and its mathematical expression," *Journal of Forensic Science*, vol. 7, pp. 56-81, 1962.
- [14] S. Mfolozi, "The Multipoint Axial Thermometry Protocol of Death-time Estimation," *Journal of Numerical Thanatochronometry*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 24-32, 2021.
- [15] D. Raneri, "Enhancing forensic investigation through the use of modern three-dimensional (3D) imaging technologies for crime scene reconstruction," *Australian Journal of Forensic Sciences*, vol. 50, no. 6, pp. 1-11, 2018.
- [16] S. Mfolozi, "Multipoint Axial Thermometry for Death-time Estimation," *Journal of Numerical Thanatochronometry*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 19-23, 2021.
- [17] J. Davey, "Observations on the temperature of the human body after death," *Researches, Physiological and Anatomical*, pp. 323-330, 1839.
- [18] C. Henßge, "Temperatur-Todeszeit-Nomogramm für Bezugsstandardbedingungen der Leichenlagerung (Temperature-death-time nomogram for reference to standard conditions of cadaver storage. German, abstract in English)," *Krim. Forensische Wiss.*, pp. 109-115, 1982.
- [19] L. Al-Alousi and R. Anderson, "Microwave thermography in forensic medicine," *Police Surgeon*, vol. 30, pp. 30-42, 1986.
- [20] L. Al-Alousi, R. Anderson and D. Land, "A non-invasive method for postmortem temperature measurements using a microwave probe," *Forensic Science International*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 34-46, 1994.
- [21] J. Burman, "On the rate of cooling of the human body after death," *Edinburg Medical Journal*, vol. 25, no. 11, pp. 993-1003, 1880.
- [22] T. Marshall, "The use of body temperature in estimating time of death," *Journal of Forensic Science*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 211-221, 1962.
- [23] F. Fiddes and T. Patten, "A percentage method for representing the fall in body temperature after death: its use in estimating the time of death," *Journal of Forensic Medicine*, vol. 5, pp. 2-15, 1958.
- [24] C. Henßge, "Die Präzision von Todeszeitachtungen durch die mathematische Beschreibung der rektalen Leichenkühlung (Precision of estimating the time of death by mathematical expression of rectal body cooling. German, summary in English)," *Zeit. Rechtsmed*, vol. 83, pp. 45-67, 1979.
- [25] C. Henßge, S. Hahn and B. Madea, "Praktische Erfahrungen mit einem Abkühlungdummy. (Practical experience with a body-cooling dummy. German, summary in English)," *Beitr. Gerichtl. Med.*, vol. 44, pp. 123-126, 1986.
- [26] C. Henßge, B. Madea and C. Pitzken, "Die Abkühlung eines Dummy unter verschiedenen Bedingungen im Vergleich zur Leichenabkühlung (The cooling of a dummy under various conditions in comparison with body cooling. German, summary in English)," *Beitr. Gerichtl. Med.*, vol. 45, pp. 145-149, 1987.
- [27] L. Wilk, R. Hoveling, G. Edelman, H. Hardy, S. van Schouwen, H. van Venrooij and M. Aalders,

"Reconstructing the time since death using non-invasive thermometry and numerical analysis," *Science Advances*, vol. 6, no. 24, pp. 1-7, 2020.

- [28] L. Wilk, G. Edelman, M. Ross, M. Clerkx, I. Dijkman, J. Melgar, R. Oostra and M. Aalders, "Individualised and non-contact post-mortem interval determination of human bodies using visible and thermal 3D imaging," *Nature*, vol. 12, no. 5997, pp. 1-10, 14 October 2021.

